

SUPPLEMENTAL TABLES

Supplemental Table 1. Action potential characteristics of hiPSC-CMC ± mAB-1 at different concentrations

	Control (n=15)	mAB-1 5 µg/ml (n=4)	mAB-1 10 µg/ml (n=10)	mAB-1 20 µg/ml (n=11)	mAB-1 30 µg/ml (n=14)	mAB-1 60 µg/ml (n=14)	P value
MDP (mV)	-70.3 ± 1.7	-62.4 ± 5.0	-68.4 ± 1.4	-59.1 ± 2.4	-59.2 ± 3.1	-55.0 ± 2.7	0.0001
APA (mV)	108.7 ± 2.7	98.6 ± 10.3	103.5 ± 3.7	90.21 ± 4.3	83.2 ± 5.9	78.5 ± 4.7	<0.0001
APD ₉₀ (ms)	548.2 ± 44.7	442.4 ± 30.7	391.6 ± 32.7	328.9 ± 37.5	321.5 ± 37.0	296.5 ± 28.6	0.0001
Frequency (bpm)	41.2 ± 4.1	67.5 ± 6.3	57.6 ± 8.7	88.2 ± 10.9	89.7 ± 8.3	109.6 ± 13.1	<0.0001

Represented are mean values ± SEM of spontaneous action potentials recorded at 37°C. P value was determined by one-way ANOVA. P<0.05 was considered statistically significant. APA = action potential amplitude; APD = action potential duration; MDP = maximum diastolic potential

Supplemental Table 2. Action potential characteristics of a pharmacological model of LQTS2 in hiPSC-CMC ± mAB-1

	LQTS2 hiPSC-CMC (n=7)	LQTS2 hiPSC-CMC + mAB-1 30 µg/ml (n=8)	P value
MDP (mV)	-60.6 ± 4.4	-57.1 ± 2.3	0.485
APA (mV)	95.5 ± 9.4	81.5 ± 4.6	0.187
APD ₉₀ (ms)	2036.1 ± 587.0	318.9 ± 50.2	0.0006
Frequency (bpm)	31.0 ± 4.4	121.9 ± 11.5	<0.0001

Represented are mean values ± SEM of spontaneous action potentials recorded at 37°C. P value was determined by one-way ANOVA. P<0.05 was considered statistically significant. APA = action potential amplitude; APD = action potential duration; LQTS2 = long QT syndrome type 2; MDP = maximum diastolic potential

Supplemental Table 3. Action potential characteristics of a pharmacological model of LQTS3 in hiPSC-CMC ± mAB-1

	LQTS3 hiPSC-CMC (n=16)	LQTS3 hiPSC-CMC + mAB-1 30 µg/ml (n=14)	P value
MDP (mV)	-76.3 ± 1.1	-72.4 ± 2.3	0.313
APA (mV)	121.6 ± 1.1	111.8 ± 4.0	0.018
APD ₉₀ (ms)	1021.0 ± 67.2	564.9 ± 47.3	<0.0001
Frequency (bpm)	24.4 ± 3.7	52.4 ± 6.4	<0.0001

Represented are mean values ± SEM of spontaneous action potentials recorded at 37°C. P value was determined by one-way ANOVA. P<0.05 was considered statistically significant. APA = action potential amplitude; APD = action potential duration; LQTS3 = long QT syndrome type 3; MDP = maximum diastolic potential

SUPPLEMENTAL FIGURES

Supplemental Figure 1

Supplemental Figure 1. Binding of mAB-1 to KCNQ1 channel peptide. Different concentrations of KCNQ1 channel peptide (serially diluted by two-fold) were injected for 120s followed by 600s of dissociation. Representative binding sensorgrams of injections performed in triplicate. The following mean association rate constant (on rate, k_a), mean dissociation rate constant (off rate, k_d) and mean equilibrium dissociation constant (K_D) values for the antibody-antigen interaction were calculated (\pm standard deviation): $k_a=9.09 \times 10^4 \pm 1.53 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $k_d=8.20 \times 10^{-4} \pm 5.34 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $K_D=9.02 \times 10^{-9} \pm 6.99 \times 10^{-10} \text{ M}$.

Supplemental Figure 2

Supplemental Figure 2. Conformational epitope mapping of mAB-1. (A) PEPperCHIP[®] peptide microarray covering the entire sequence of KCNQ1 protein translated into overlapping constrained cyclic peptides of 7, 10 and 13 amino acid lengths. In total the microarray contained 2043 different peptides printed in duplicate, framed by additional HA peptides (YPYDVPDYAG, 134 spots) serving as

control. The microarrays were probed with 0.1 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ mAB-1 followed by staining with anti-mouse IgG (red) and anti-HA IgG (green). Sequences of reactive spots (red) are shown. Residues potentially contributing to antibody binding are highlighted in blue. (B) Intensity plots of the peptide microarray demonstrating clear epitope peaks for the consensus motif VEEG. The arginine (R) amino acid preceding this sequence may contribute to antibody binding as well. Significantly weaker interactions were found for peptides with the consensus motifs FGTE and VDGY presumably due to cross-reactions based on minor sequence homologies (underlined amino acid positions). Nonetheless, both peptide sequences are located intracellularly and are therefore not readily accessible to circulating antibodies.

Supplemental Figure 3. Effect of mAB-1 monoclonal antibody on human iPSC-cardiomyocytes (hiPSC-CMCs) in the context of pharmacological LQTS type 2. (A) Representative action potentials recorded in hiPSC-CMCs challenged with E-4031 showing early afterdepolarizations (EADs), arrhythmic beating degenerating in beating arrest. (B) Representative action potentials recorded in hiPSC-CMCs treated with 30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ mAB-1 and challenged with E-4031. (C) Bars represent the incidence of EADs, arrhythmic beating and beating arrest in hiPSC-CMCs challenged with E-4031 (n = 7) \pm 30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ mAB-1 (n = 8). (D) Bars represent the mean $\text{APD}_{90} \pm \text{SEM}$ of hiPSC-CMCs challenged with E-4031 (n = 7) \pm 30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ mAB-1 (n = 8). *** P<0.001.